

VOCATIONAL GUIDANCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IS AN IMPORTANT
PEDAGOGICAL PROCESS

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Abstract. *The following article analyzes the initial pedagogical processes in the professional orientation of students of primary education, reflecting on the content of the pedagogical skills of the teacher, knowledge and skills of choosing a profession, tasks, as well as personality traits in choosing a profession, student psychology, criteria indicating the readiness of students to choose a profession, age stages of preparing students for*

Keywords: *teacher, student, primary education, profession, career orientation, psychology of young Times.*

ПРОФОРЕНТАЦИЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ – ВАЖНЫЙ
ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЙ ПРОЦЕСС

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются начальные педагогические процессы в направлении учащихся начальных классов к профессии, и в этом процессе анализируются педагогические умения, знания и умения учителя, связанные с выбором профессии, задач, а также особенности личности в выборе профессии. , психология студента, критерии, свидетельствующие о готовности студентов к выбору профессии, содержание возрастных этапов подготовки студентов к выбору профессии.*

Ключевые слова: *Учитель, ученик, начальное образование, профессия, профориентация, психология молодежи.*

In recent years, the Republic of Uzbekistan has implemented large-scale reforms in the education system, including all areas. The effect of these changes, the worthy place of our country among the progressive states, is inextricably linked, first of all, with the development of the field of Science and education.

Today it should be noted that the contribution of our teachers and coaches to the worthy maturation of our children, who, having mastered modern knowledge and professions, foreign languages, are stepping into life with great hope and confidence, are the decisive force of our tomorrow. The elementary education teacher not only gives students the initial knowledge of the world of science, but also directs students to the profession in this process. Since childhood, the student is fond of any profession,] dreams of it, imagines himself as the owner of that profession.

The teacher has a great role in ensuring the realism of this vision. Somehow, the teacher is supposedly a “wizard”, an incomparable mentor in the imagination of a child who has not yet perfectly formed.

All forms and methods of work on vocational guidance of primary education students should serve the purposeful career choices of students. When establishing vocational orientation work at school, it is recommended to make the most of the elements of new pedagogical technology, such as pedagogical play, independent thoughts, along with traditional practical training, conversation, dialogue discussions. Primary education students are still far from choosing a profession. However, the job of choosing the right profession between them should be such a basis that the interests, thoughts and intentions of students in the upper classes for the profession will then develop on the basis of this. Beistisno has personality traits that are necessary and important for all professions, these are:

- hard work, respect for the working people in all professions and specialties;
- understanding and understanding the need to work;
- be able to recycle and control their work;
- to properly organize the workplace, to be full of work and disciplined;
- tolerance, perseverance, being able to choose the most rational way to complete the task;
- saving materials and time, and so on.

All these qualities and qualities should be formed in students from the first grade . It is necessary to gradually bring children into the world of professions, teach them to be able to embody in this world. The teacher notices some of its features, inclinations in the process of observing the student in classes, talking to him, analyzing the product of the child's activities, these can be the main factor in determining the profession later, after completing the corresponding work on the development of qualities. In order to choose a profession, the student must have the skill of being able to assess his capabilities, that is, intelligence, interest, knowledge of various professions, information about the possibilities, future of these professions. The orientation of the individual to the profession is carried out through special scientific practical activities, at the stages of the formation of students as a person, the person and society, that is, the family, are considered as a single system. Criteria indicating the readiness of students to choose a profession:

- cognitive (having information);
- the criterion of interest in the profession is a practical criterion .

In order for the correct choice of a profession to correspond to the objective arguments, interests, inclinations, abilities and capabilities of each growing generation, it is necessary to take

into account its health, assimilation and emotions, which in socially useful and productive work will be expressed and manifested more than anyone else. And the premature identification of the professionally important qualities of a child can later allow him to correctly choose a profession based on his characteristics, successfully master it, achieve high results in labor. Studies conducted by many scientists show that in about 30% of schoolchildren, stable interests in relation to the chosen profession are formed as early as primary classes. The task of the teacher is to identify the interests of students as early as possible and develop these interests in accordance with the requirements and needs of society, to create conditions for the harmonious maturation of the human personality in every possible way. One of the main goals of labor education in the elementary grades is to make sure that labor for a person in students is the first necessity, social duty, that solid and deep knowledge is needed to master any profession. Love for work and the desire to work can only be brought up in labor. Therefore, about 80 percent of the time in labor education classes is allocated for practical work. The study of the personality of students is closely related to their upbringing. The teacher, noticing the individual characteristics of the student, can find methods for the development of existing talent badges in him, eliminate negative aspects of his behavior, etc. k. In some children, the predisposition to the profession is well manifested, in most children this thing is not detected at once. It is important that the teacher identifies the goals of talent in the child, helps in the development and formation of his abilities. As mentioned above, the work of professional orientation is an integral component of the educational process. This work, which begins with the lower classes, is necessary for society, helps to cultivate a stable interest in professions corresponding to the characteristics of each person.

The presence of an interest in labor and a desire to work is one of the most important indicators of the maturity of an individual. Extracurricular and extracurricular work helps students in many ways to consciously choose a profession, develop their creative abilities, develop interest in work in them in Material Production, Science, Technology, and the like. In the work of vocational guidance, which is carried out in extracurricular activities, several stages can be indicated depending on the age and cognitive characteristics of students.

Working with students of the first stage (I-IV) class — forms social interests in labor in the field of material production, forms in students a positive attitude towards Labor as a whole, and most importantly — such a reaction to physical labor, respect the name worker, the desire to give joy to the surrounding people with his own labor that he can and receive spiritual satisfaction from it. Work on this will be carried out according to a previously drawn up plan. In accordance with this plan, organizing an excursion is envisaged to organize conversations about the most

popular professions for students of rural schools in collective farm, for students of urban schools in enterprises, for the work of parents and their success in labor.

During the excursions, the main attention is paid to the work of people participating in the production process, to the weapons of labor that they are giving to obtain finished products from raw materials, the role of labor in the marriage of society and some people is emphasized.

The Second Stage (V-VII) is a stage in which students of grades are encouraged to do something. It is known that in the educational process, interest in knowledge in students is usually formed before interest in the profession. Therefore, at this stage in the field of professional orientation, it is important to arouse the interest in students in knowing the types of work (working with techniques, working with objects of nature and the like). At this stage of professional orientation, extracurricular activities, quizzes, games on techniques and labor (technical creativity and agricultural experimentalism) should play a big role. At this stage, the formation of social goals in students continues, while professional orientation begins. The third stage (mainly VIII-XI) covers students of grades — at this stage, students examine their strength in concrete labor, and students' interests and inclinations towards the profession are further formed. At this stage, students reinforce their professional intentions with practical skills and qualifications in some common professions. This stage ends with the choice of a concrete profession, the determination of ways to master it. It is noteworthy for this stage that students work in circles according to their interests (objects, objects-techniques, production-techniques, etc.). In order to further improve the process of professional orientation of primary education students, the following proposals are recommended:

- focus on individual work in career guidance;
- Organization of round tables on the topic;
- introduction to audio-video materials of various professions;
- directing extracurricular activities to the choice of profession;
- Organization of meetings with specialists from different fields; – Organization of cultural events; - Organization of the corner of professions and organization of traveling exhibitions on this topic.

As a conclusion, it can be noted that directing students to the right profession on time is a guarantee of the development of the country.

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